

Optimization of Surface Grinding Process Parameters of BÖHLER K340 ISODUR

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Abstract

This paper presents a study of surface roughness (R_a) and material removal rate (MMR) obtained in surface grinding of hardened (58-62) BÖHLER K340 ISIODUR die steel under flood cooling. In this work, empirical models are developed for surface roughness and material removal rate by considering Depth of Cut, feed and table feed as control factors using full factorial design and Response Surface Methodology for design of experiment. In response surface methodology and full factorial design 13, 27 experiments were conducted in the surface grinding machine. The surface roughness values were entered in the Minitab19 software and the optimal solution was obtained. The optimum parameter was attained at the maximum overall desirability. An analysis of variance (ANOVA) was conducted to confirm the model adequacy. From the results of the study, for equal weights of responses, the corresponding optimal values of the input parameters depth of cut, cross-feed and table speed were found to be 7 μ m, 150 m/min, 18 m/min respectively.

Keywords: Surface Grinding, Surface Roughness, Response Surface Methodology, Factorial Design, MRR, BÖHLER K340 ISIODUR

1. Introduction

Grinding is a finishing process, broadly used in manufacturing of components requiring fine tolerances, good surface finish and higher dimensional and geometrical accuracy. Compared with other material removal processes as an example of turning, milling and boring, the grinding process is more complex and more difficult to control. In addition to the static parameters of the grinding machine tool, there are many dynamic factors that contribute to resulting dimensional accuracy. Surface finish is very important for parts which will be in contact with other metal surfaces. The lower value of surface roughness causes less wear and friction. The lowest value of surface roughness gives the best surface finish. The surface quality produced in surface grinding is influenced by various parameters such as i wheel parameters – abrasives, grain size, grade, structure, binder, shape and dimension; ii Work piece parameters – fracture mode, mechanical properties and chemical composition; iii process parameters – wheel speed, depth of cut, table speed and dressing condition; iv Machine parameters – static and dynamic characteristics, spindle system, and table system.

BÖHLER K340 ISIODUR tool steel is regarded as a key material in high performance engineering applications such as in the mold-and-die industry; for use as industrial cutting tools, gauges, and machine parts exposed to wear and injection screws; in aerospace and automotive industries; medical appliances; heavy engineering; and tools in the manufacturing industry. This is due to its superior properties like high wear resistance, compressive strength, temperature resistance, and narrow tolerances as well as its high strength-to-weight ratio. However, the manufactured parts demand for high geometrical and dimensional intricacy—which raises the necessity of using a grinding operation.

In this case, two performance characteristics of surface grinding process, namely MRR and R_a are considered for optimization. MRR and R_a indicate the production rate and quality of the product respectively. The common practice in the industries is that the selection of grinding parameters is made based on either operator's experience or grinding parameter tables provided by the manufacturers. However, such criterion does not guarantee neither high production rate nor good surface quality. Therefore, there is a need to develop a methodology to optimize MRR and R_a [20].

2. Literature survey

The following section discusses the major contribution of the researchers with regard to the optimization of surface grinding process.

Aqib Mashood Khan et al. [6] investigated on surface grinding of AISI D2 steel and used Grey–Taguchi method and Response Surface Methodology (RSM) for the multi-objective optimization. It was found that the developed models are statistically significant, with optimum conditions of depth of cut of 15 m., table speed of 3 m/min, cutting speed 25 m/min, and MQL flow rate 250 mL/h.

Saraan et al. [7] experimental studied on the enhancement of conventional flood cooling by adding nano droplets which about 5 Nm of average particle size for using surface grinding of EN-31 steel. Taguchi L36 orthogonal array used for Design the experiment. Here the control factors are feeds, in feeds and various cutting fluids when surface grinding EN31 steel were considered to observe the response of surface roughness and cutting zone temperature.

M. Aravind et al. [8] used to Taguchi Method (L27 orthogonal array) And Response Surface Methodology(Box- Behnken method) to Optimization of Surface Grinding Process Parameters of AISI 1035 steel plates.

Bruno Kenta Sato et al. [9] evoked Novel comparison concept between CBN and Al_2O_3 grinding process for eco-friendly production. In this study, Minimal Quantity of Lubrication was developed to achieve green manufacturing in machining process and parameters of cutting fluid flow, grinding wheel type and wheel cleaning system were evaluated to achieve the maximum potential of this technique in grinding process.

Taghi Tawakoli et al. [10] conducted to study the influence of the abrasive and coolant lubricant types on the minimum quantity lubrication (MQL) grinding performance. One type of CBN and three types of conventional wheels (corundum) have been tested. The tests have been performed in presence of fluid, air jet and eleven types of coolant lubricants, as well as, in dry condition. The results indicate that the finest surface quality and lower grinding forces could be obtained while grinding with CBN wheel.

Hoang Tie Dung et al. [11] studied on surface roughness of work piece when grinding SKD11 and SUJ2 steels using Al_2O_3 and CBN wheels.

Jeffrey Badger et al. [12] studied on comparison of specific energy, wheel wear, surface-generation mechanisms and surface characteristics when grinding with Al₂O₃ and CBN to achieve a given surface roughness and new concept is developed, the nominal bond shear stress, which can be used to quantify the risk of grit fracture or bond fracture in a single grit. The fundamental relationships between grit size, grit sharpness and contact mechanisms are discussed and practical recommendations are given.

Konrad Wegener et al. [13] studied on recent developments in grinding machines.

Ch. N. V. Jaswanth et al. [14] experiment performed on Surface Grinding of HC-HCr Steel using Dry and MQL Techniques used Response Surface Methodology to optimization carried out for minimization of surface roughness and temperature.

P.P.Pereverzev et al. [15] developed a mathematical model is for the grinding force in cylindrical plunge grinding that allows for the grinding conditions, the size of the flank wear land areas formed on the grinding wheel cutting grains, the properties of the work material, and the geometrical parameters of the grinding tool and work surface and obtained a formula for calculating the stock removal rate as a function of the degree of dulling (glazing) of the grinding wheel.

J. Vivancos et al. [16] experiment model developed for surface roughness in high-speed side milling with carbide end mill coated with (Al, Ti, Si)N cutter of hardened (61–62 HRC) Böhler K340 die steels. The influence of cutting speed, feed per tooth, axial depth and radial depth of cut is studied using a 2⁴⁺¹ fractional factorial design of experiments. Finally, it has been determined the factors and interactions that are statistically more significant for modeling the surface roughness R_a .

Todkar et al. [17] a vibration device has been designed and developed in which the work piece is subjected to vibration up to a frequency of 1 kHz and amplitude of 2.5 μ m. And investigated the feasibility of drilling deep micro holes in difficult-to cut Tungsten carbide by means of low frequency work piece vibration-assisted micro-Electro Discharge Machining (micro-EDM) of K340 Steel.

Roy R. et al. [18] carried out Multi-Response Optimization of Surface Grinding Process Parameters of AISI 4140 Alloy Steel Using Response Surface Methodology and Desirability Function under Dry and Wet Conditions.

Rajesh Choudhary et al. [19] have investigated of Machining Performance and Surface Integrity of AISI D2 Die Steel Machined Using Electrical Discharge Surface Grinding Process. They have used Taguchi method (L27 Taguchi orthogonal) was applied to identify the optimum levels of process parameters for each performance characteristics individually.

M. Janardhan [20] used Response surface methodology (RSM) for modeling and non-dominated sorting genetic algorithm-II (NSGA-II) for multi-objective optimization of a surface grinding process on AISI 4340 steel.

3. Methodology

3.1 Work piece material

The work piece material selected for investigation is BÖHLER K340 ISIODUR cold die steel. BÖHLER K340 ISIODUR (Quenched and Tempered, an 8% chromium steel is produced using the electro-slag re-melting (ERS) method. BÖHLER K340 ISIODUR Chemical compositions are presented in table1. The work piece material are

used in dimensions of 120mm×80mm×30mm rectangular work piece with a hardness of 58 ~ 62 which permits to carry out 27 different experiments on the same work piece, two on each lateral face.

Table 1. Chemical of composition BÖHLER K340 ISIODUR (nominal in wt. %)

C	Si	Mn	Cr	Mo	V	
1.10	0.90	0.40	8.30	2.10	0.50	+Nb, Al

Fig. 1. Finish BÖHLER K340 ISIODUR Material

3.2 Experimental set-up

The experiments were performed on NC surface grinding machine KENT 63 with single point diamond dresser and water soluble synthetic oil, which is having grinding Wheel of size 350 x 50 x 127. Experimental setup shown in figure2. The material of grinding wheel is aluminum oxide (Al_2O_3) with A60 L5 V10 specifications. Spindle speed is 1800 RPM. To reduce the thermal damage which will be produced during the interaction of work material and grinding wheel, coolant is used. It helps to reduce the heat as well as to wash away the grinded metal powder.

Fig. 2. Experimental Set up

3.3 Surface roughness testing instrument

The work piece surface roughness was measured with a Taylor–Hobson Surtronic S128 Surface Roughness Tester that is shown in figure 3. An evaluation length is 0.25mm to 25.0mm, and a nominally $5\mu\text{m}$ stylus tip default used in conjunction with a 0.8 Gaussian cut-off filter and a bandwidth ratio of 300:1 to evaluate the R_a roughness parameter. A stylus speed of 1 mm/s was used in conjunction with a 0.8mN static stylus force, and the stylus cone angle used is 90° . The uncertainty of the Roughness tester is given, from the certificate of Calibration of the manufacturer, by $\pm (2\% + 0.004 \mu\text{m})$ for R_a .

Fig. 3. Taylor–Hobson Surtronic S128 Surface Roughness Tester

3.4 Material removal rate (MMR)

The material removal rate can be found out by the difference of the initial reading and the final readings of the thickness of the material of BÖHLER K340 ISIODUR steel. The amount of material removed per unit time (theoretically) from the work piece by machining is determined by the following equation.

Measurement of MRR: $f \cdot d \cdot b$

Where, MRR = Material Removal Rate (mm³/min)

f = feed rate (mm/min), d = depth of cut (mm), b =width of cut (mm)

3.5 Design of experiments (DOE)

The design of experiments (DOE) technique is a powerful tool that allows us to analyze the influence of certain process variables over other specified variables, which are usually called response variables. These response variables are unknown functions of the former design variables, which are also known as design factors. Table 2 shows the design factors and their corresponding selected variation levels.

Table 2 Factors and their levels for surface grinding of BÖHLER K340 ISIODUR.

S.. No.	Process Parameters	Level 1	Level 2	Level 3
1	Depth of Cut(μm)	7	11	15
2	Feed (mm/min.)	150	200	250
3	Table Feed (m/min)	14	18	24

3.5.1. Full factorial design

The design that chosen was a full factorial Design. One of the most widely used designs of experiments is the factorial design, which consists of experimenting with all the possible combinations of variables and levels. Find out numbers of runs and data analyze using Minitab19, consequently carrying out a total of 27 experiments. Table 3 shows the design matrix for the full factorial design, and the Ra values obtained during the corresponding experiments.

Table 3 Design matrix for the Full Factorial Design.

Experiment No.	Depth of Cut (μm)	Feed (mm/min)	Table Feed (m/min)	R_a (μm)
1	15	150	18	0.50
2	11	200	18	0.44
3	7	200	24	0.35
4	15	250	14	0.53
5	7	200	14	0.31
6	11	200	24	0.47
7	11	150	24	0.44
8	15	200	24	0.60
9	7	150	14	0.32
10	7	250	14	0.34
11	15	150	24	0.54
12	7	150	18	0.31
13	15	200	14	0.52
14	7	250	24	0.38
15	15	200	18	0.55
16	7	150	24	0.35
17	7	250	18	0.36
18	7	200	18	0.34
19	11	150	18	0.40
20	15	250	24	0.66
21	11	150	14	0.41
22	15	250	18	0.62
23	11	250	14	0.45
24	11	200	14	0.43
25	15	150	14	0.47
26	11	250	24	0.48
27	11	250	18	0.52

3.5.2. Response surface methodology

Response Surface Methodology (RSM) is a combination of mathematical and statistical technique that is useful for the modeling and analysis of problem in which a response of interest is influenced by several variables

and the objective is to optimize the response. In RSM, it is possible to represent independent process parameters in quantitative form as:

$$Y = f(X1, X2, X3...X) \pm e \quad (1)$$

Where, Y is the response (yield), 'f' is the response function, 'e' is the experimental error, and X1, X2, X3 . . . X are independent parameters. By plotting the expected response of Y, a surface, known as the response surface is obtained. The form of 'f' is unknown and maybe complicated. Thus, RSM aims at approximating 'f' by a suitable lower order polynomial in some region of the independent process variables. If the response can be well modeled by a linear function of the independent variables, the function can be written as:

$$Y = C0 + C1X1 + C2X2 + \dots + CnXn \pm e \quad (2)$$

However, if a curvature appears in the system, then a higher order polynomial such as the quadratic model may be written as:

$$Y = C0 + \sum_{i=0}^n CiXi + \sum_{i=0}^n CiXi^2 \pm e \quad (3)$$

Response surface methodology (RSM) with central composite design (CCD) has been considered for the modeling and analysis of the performance measures of the ground work piece. The total numbers of experiments were selected as thirteen. For two factors and the number of center blocks was selected as 1.

Table 4 Design matrix for Response Surface Methodology

Experiment No.	Depth of Cut (μm)	Feed (mm/min)	R_a (μm)	MMR (mm^3/min)
1	9	154	0.32	0.90
2	10	175	0.41	0.77
3	11	200	0.46	0.7
4	9	196	0.34	0.83
5	9	175	0.36	0.85
6	8	175	0.30	0.90
7	11	150	0.39	0.75
8	9	175	0.35	0.86
9	7	200	0.34	0.88
10	9	175	0.34	0.83
11	7	150	0.30	0.92
12	9	175	0.36	0.86
13	9	175	0.35	0.85

Material removal rate and surface roughness values are given in table4for 13 experiments according to different control levels. Table4 shows the design matrix for response surface methodology, and the R_a and MRR values obtained during the corresponding experiments.

4. Result and discussion

In this section, surface roughness and material removal are analyzed by the experimental investigation, statistical analysis, mathematical modeling, and graphical plots through conducting the experiment according to the full factorial design method and response surface methodology method find out their response parameters R_a , MMR values shown in table 4 and table 5 respectively.

4.1. Optimization using full factorial design

Table 5 shows each of the estimated effects and interactions. It also shows the standard error of each of the effects, which measures their sampling error. In this case, five effects have P -values less than 0.05, which indicates significant for a confident level of 95%. And P -values greater than 0.05, which means model terms not significant. The ANOVA includes the significant terms along with adequacy measures R^2 , Adj. R^2 and predicted R^2 is close to '1' indicating the adequacy of resulting model for all considered environments.

Table 5 Analysis of Variance for R_a

Source	DF	Adj SS	Adj MS	F-Value	P-Value
Model	7	0.246135	0.035162	116.57	0.000
Linear	3	0.242372	0.080791	267.83	0.000
Depth of Cut	1	0.209105	0.209105	693.20	0.000
Feed	1	0.020211	0.020211	67.00	0.000
Table Feed	1	0.013056	0.013056	43.28	0.000
2-Way Interactions	3	0.005981	0.001994	6.61	0.003
Depth of Cut*Feed	1	0.003475	0.003475	11.52	0.003
Depth of Cut*Table Feed	1	0.002284	0.002284	7.57	0.013
Feed*Table Feed	1	0.000222	0.000222	0.74	0.401
3-Way Interactions	1	0.000300	0.000300	1.00	0.331
Depth of Cut*Feed*Table Feed	1	0.000300	0.000300	1.00	0.331
Error	19	0.005731	0.000302		
Total	26	0.251867			
S		R-sq	R-sq(adj)	R-sq(pred)	
0.0173681		97.72%	96.89%	94.96%	

The model to represent R_a depicts that depth of cut, feed, table feed, and interaction of Depth of Cut*Feed, Depth of Cut*Table Feed are the most influencing parameters in order of significance. Following regression equations were obtained in terms of encoded factors.

$$\begin{aligned}
 R_a = & 0.058 + 0.0201 \text{ Depth of Cut} + 0.00068 \text{ Feed} + 0.0078 \text{ Table Feed} \\
 & - 0.000030 \text{ Depth of Cut*Feed} - 0.00053 \text{ Depth of Cut*Table Feed} \\
 & - 0.000050 \text{ Feed*Table Feed} + 0.000006 \text{ Depth of Cut*Feed*Table Feed}
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{4}$$

Figure 4 shows Standardized Pareto Chart for R_a that shows significant parameters effected of R_a and The normal probability plots of residuals for R_a is shown in the Figure 5. From this plot, it can be concluding that the residuals lies on a straight line which implies that the errors are distributed normally and the developed regression models are well fitted with the observed values. This shows that the models are adequate without any violation of independence or constant assumption.

Fig. 4. Standardized Pareto Chart for R_a

Fig. 5. Normal Probability Plot for R_a

The influence of each control factor can be more clearly presented with response graph Figure 6. These figure reveal the level to be chosen for the ideal cutting parameters (the level with the highest point on the graphs), as well as the relative effect each parameter has on the R_a (the general slope of the line). As seen in the R_a effects graph Figure 6 the slope of the line which connects between the levels can clearly shows the power of influence of each control factor. Especially the depth of cut and feed has a strong effect on the surface roughness. The table feed has lower effect as evidenced by the shallow shape of the lines.

Fig. 6. Main effect plot for Ra

4.2. Optimization using response surface methodology

Experiment conducting through full factorial design, observed R_a value mainly depend on two factor one is depth of cut and another one feed. Then created another model by using response surface methodology in which range of depth of cut and feed rate curtailed. After conducting experiment according to Design matrix for Response Surface Methodology, the output response R_a and MRR measured and entered into design layout table 5. The models were evaluated and ANOVA table for response surface design were obtained.

4.2.1. Analysis of variance for R_a and MRR

The analysis of variance (ANOVA) of response surface quadratic model for surface roughness and metal removal rate were shown in Table 6 and Table 7 respectively.

Table 6 Analysis of Variance for Ra

Source	DF	Adj SS	Adj MS	F-Value	P-Value
Model	5	0.021682	0.004336	18.50	0.001
Linear	2	0.020038	0.010019	42.73	0.000
Depth of Cut(μm)	1	0.017067	0.017067	72.79	0.000
Feed(mm/min)	1	0.002971	0.002971	12.67	0.009
Square	2	0.001419	0.000709	3.03	0.113
Depth of Cut(μm)*Depth of Cut(μm)	1	0.001031	0.001031	4.40	0.074
Feed(mm/min)*Feed(mm/min)	1	0.000001	0.000001	0.00	0.959
2-Way Interaction	1	0.000225	0.000225	0.96	0.360
Depth of Cut(μm)*Feed(mm/min)	1	0.000225	0.000225	0.96	0.360

Error	7	0.001641	0.000234		
Lack-of-Fit	3	0.001361	0.000454	6.48	0.051
Pure Error	4	0.000280	0.000070		
Total	12	0.023323			
S	R-sq	R-sq(adj)	R-sq(pred)		
0.0153118	92.96%	87.94%	56.52%		

Analysis of variance (ANOVA) is then employed to test the significance of the developed models. The multiple regression coefficients (R^2) of the second order model for surface roughness and metal removal rate were found to be 92.96% and 94.80% respectively. The R^2 values are very high, close to one, indicates that the second order models are adequate to represent the machining process. The "Pred. R-Squared" of 56.52% is in reasonable agreement with the "Adj. R-Squared" of 87.94% in case of surface roughness. Similarly in case of MRR, the "Pred. R-Squared" of 59.48% is in reasonable agreement with the "Adj. R Squared" of 91.09%. The model F-value of 72.79 and 105.56 for Ra and MRR implies that the models are significant. There is only a 0.01% chance that a "Model F-Value" this large could occur due to noise. The P value for both the models is lower than 0.05 (at 95% confidence level) indicates that the both the models could be considered to be statistically significant. The model made to represent MRR and SR depicts that depth of cut, feed, depth of cut depth of cut, and interaction of grit size and depth of cut are the most influencing parameters in order of significance.

Table 7 Analysis of Variance for MRR

Source	DF	Adj SS	Adj MS	F-Value	P-Value
Model	5	0.046423	0.009285	25.52	0.000
Linear	2	0.042492	0.021246	58.41	0.000
Depth of Cut(μ m)	1	0.038400	0.038400	105.56	0.000
Feed(mm/min)	1	0.004092	0.004092	11.25	0.012
Square	2	0.003906	0.001953	5.37	0.039
Depth of Cut(μ m)*Depth of Cut(μ m)	1	0.002299	0.002299	6.32	0.040
Feed(mm/min)*Feed(mm/min)	1	0.000108	0.000108	0.30	0.602
2-Way Interaction	1	0.000025	0.000025	0.07	0.801
Depth of Cut(μ m)*Feed(mm/min)	1	0.000025	0.000025	0.07	0.801
Error	7	0.002546	0.000364		
Lack-of-Fit	3	0.001946	0.000649	4.33	0.096
Pure Error	4	0.000600	0.000150		
Total	12	0.048969			
S	R-sq	R-sq(adj)	R-sq(pred)		
0.0190726	94.80%	91.09%	59.48%		

In the present study, empirical models of second order for the responses, Surface roughness (R_a) and MRR in terms of selected machining parameters in actual factors were developed using RSM. The developed models are

subsequently used for optimization of the grinding process. To determine the regression coefficients of the developed model, the statistical analysis software, Minitab19 is used. Following regression equations 5 and 6 were obtained in terms of encoded factors

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Ra}(\mu\text{m}) = & 0.625 - 0.0927 \text{ Depth of Cut}(\mu\text{m}) - 0.00073 \text{ Feed}(\text{mm}/\text{min}) \\ & + 0.00517 \text{ Depth of Cut}(\mu\text{m}) * \text{Depth of Cut}(\mu\text{m}) + 0.000001 \text{ Feed}(\text{mm}/\text{min}) * \text{Feed}(\text{mm}/\text{min}) \\ & + 0.000150 \text{ Depth of Cut}(\mu\text{m}) * \text{Feed}(\text{mm}/\text{min}) \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{MRR}(\text{mm}/\text{cycle}) = & 0.347 + 0.1078 \text{ Depth of Cut}(\mu\text{m}) + 0.00343 \text{ Feed}(\text{mm}/\text{min}) \\ & - 0.00773 \text{ Depth of Cut}(\mu\text{m}) * \text{Depth of Cut}(\mu\text{m}) \\ & - 0.000012 \text{ Feed}(\text{mm}/\text{min}) * \text{Feed}(\text{mm}/\text{min}) \\ & - 0.000050 \text{ Depth of Cut}(\mu\text{m}) * \text{Feed}(\text{mm}/\text{min}) \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

The normal probability plots of residuals for Ra and MRR are shown in the Figure 7 and Figure 8 respectively.

Fig. 7. Normal Probability Plot of residuals for Ra

Fig.8. Normal Probability Plot of residuals for MRR

Fig.9.Main effect plot for R_a

Fig.10.Main effect plot for MRR

From these plots, it can be concluding that the residuals lies on a straight line which implies that the errors are distributed normally and the developed regression models are well fitted with the observed values. Figure 9 and 10 shows the average value of R_a and MRR respectively for different levels of selected input parameters. It can observed that R_a (Smaller is better) value decrease with decrease depth of cut and feed, while MRR (Larger is better) decrease with increase depth of cut and feed.

4.3. Optimal result

In the present study, objective is to minimize the surface roughness to maximize MRR. Using RSM optimization multi-objective response. The responses SR & MRR have successfully predicted up to the adequate level 0.2976 microns and 0.9226 mm/cycle at combination of variable as depth of cut 7 μm , and feed rate 150mm/min using multi-objective response optimization technique as shown in figure 11.

Fig.11. Response optimization plot (Ra & MRR)

5. Conclusions

The present work proposed a methodology to determine the optimal machining parameters to achieve high production rate and good surface quality of machined components. Experimentation on surface grinding process with BÖHLER K340 ISIODUR die steel as work piece material was conducted with Full Factorial Design and Response Surface Methodology as per design of experiments. Based on the results of the experimental investigation, the following comparative conclusions for surface grinding can be done.

1. The factors that most affect the surface roughness (R_a) parameter are depth of cut and feed rate.
2. Material removal rate were found decreasing as the depth of cut increase because of K340 hardened die steel and grinding wheel also medium strength, during cutting interaction abrasive particles goes round off that not removed material as per given depth of cut.
3. The minimum surface roughness (R_a) and MRR were obtained at combination of variable factors as depth of cut $7\mu\text{m}$, feed rate 150mm/min using multi-objective response optimization RSM technique. The obtained surface roughness value most suitable for super finishing process.

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